

POLAND

POLAND

PSYCHOLOGICAL INTERPRETATION OF THE STAGES OF ONTOGENESIS

Avezov Olmos Ravshanovich¹

Associate Professor of

Shavkatova Shakhnoza Pulot qizi²

Student of

¹Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute

²Bukhara State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7030508>

ANNOTATION

The article covers the period from the birth of a person to the end of his life. It covers biological and psychological aspects of development. Thoughts, reflections and research on age periods and their classifications are discussed. Comprehensive information is given about the physical, cognitive and social development of people from childhood to old age.

Key words: Maturity, perfection, stability, cognitive, zygote, embryo, motor, gene, hormone, fear, trust, hope.

INTRODUCTION

When and how do we develop during life from the womb to the grave? Almost all of us started walking at the age of 1 and started talking at the age of 2. As children, we were engaged in social games in preparation for life. As adults, we all smile, cry, love and hate, and sometimes we wonder if we're going to die one day. Developmental psychology studies how people develop physically, cognitively, and socially from childhood to old age. It has three main scientific research centers:

1. Maturation and Nurture: How do our genetic heritage (our nature) and experience (our upbringing) influence our development?
2. Stages of perfection: is development a gradual, continuous process, like riding a car, or is it a sequence of discrete steps, like climbing a flight of stairs?
3. Stability – Change: Do our early personality traits persist throughout life, or do we become different as we age?

These questions concern all of us. Because the only complex, completely unstudied creature is man. The development of its structure is equally interesting to everyone.

Literature analysis and methodology

Nothing is more natural than self-created species. Nothing is exempt. In humans, this process begins when a woman's ovary releases a mature egg—the equivalent of this cell cycle at the end. Perinatal development. More than half of the fertilized eggs, called zygotes, live for the first 2 weeks. During the first week

of one cell division, one cell becomes 2, then 4, until a zygote of about 100 cells is formed. Then the cells began to differentiate - they specialized in structure and function. About 10 days after conception, the zygote approaches the mother's uterine wall, which begins at about 37 weeks of human intercourse. The inner cells of the zygote become an embryo. During the next 6 weeks, the organs begin to form and function. The heart begins to beat. Within 9 weeks after the birth of the fetus, the embryo becomes a human being. Now it is a fetus (Latin for "offspring" or "young"). In the sixth month, organs such as the stomach have developed enough to sustain the life of a premature fetus.

Perfection, a newborn baby. After surviving the perinatal risk, we acquired automatic reservoirs that were perfectly suited to our survival as newborns. We pulled our hands away to get rid of the pain. If the scarf on our face prevents us from breathing, we turn our head to the side and rub it. New parents are often afraid of the sequence of their baby's feeding reflexes. When something touches their cheeks, babies turn toward the touch, open their mouths, and root vigorously for the nipple. Having found it, they automatically close and start sucking, which in itself requires a coordinated sequence of tongue swallowing and breathing. A hungry baby may cry if it cannot find satisfaction. Such behavior of parents is very unpleasant and very useful to relieve. Within a few days after birth, the neural networks in our brain are covered with the smell of our mother's body. Thus, a one-week-old nursing baby placed between a gauze pad will pass from the smell of its mother, and from another nursing mother to the smell of its own mother's pillow. If at 3 weeks, if given a beeper that sometimes records the voice of the mother, and sometimes the voice of an unfamiliar woman, the baby will ask louder when it hears the voice of the now familiar mother. It is also known that babies pay more attention to the faces of people and animals than to their bodies, and children spend different amounts of time on this.

Motor development.. The developing brain enables physical coordination of the body. As the child's muscles and nervous system mature, more complex abilities appear. With occasional exceptions, the sequence of physical (motor) development is universal. Babies roll over before sitting unsupported, and they usually walk on all fours. Such behavior reflects a mature nervous system, not imitation; even blind children crawl before walking.

But there are individual differences in timing. For example, in the United States, 25 percent of all babies are walking by 11 months, 50 percent within a week of their first birthday, and 90 percent by 15 months. The recommended sleep-to-

sleep position for babies (putting the baby's legs in danger during sleep) is related to later walking, not earlier walking. Genes play a major role in direct development. Identical twins usually start sitting up and walking around the same day (Wilson). Maturation, which includes the rapid development of the cerebellum at the back of the brain, allows learning to walk from the age of 1.

Piaget's research led to the idea that a child's mind develops in several stages, from the simple reflexes of a newborn to the abstract thinking of an adult. So an 8-year-old child can understand things that are incomprehensible, for example, "getting an idea is like a light turning on in your head." But our adult minds are also busy thinking that 8-year-olds haven't learned. Piaget's main idea is that the driving force of our intellectual development is the constant struggle to understand our experiences: "Children are active thinkers who are constantly striving to create advanced understandings of the world." As we grow up, we build countless schemas, from cats and dogs to the concept of love. Piaget's proposed two other concepts to explain how we use and adapt our schemas. First, we absorb new experiences - we interpret them in terms of current understanding (schemas). For example, a child with a simple schema for a cow may refer to all four-legged animals as cows. But as we interact with the world, we adapt or accommodate our schemas to incorporate information provided by new experiences. Thus, the child soon learns that the initial schema of the cow is very broad and capable of identifying categories.

Youth

Stanley Hall (1904), one of the first psychologists to describe adolescence, believed that this tension between biological maturity and social dependence creates a period of "stress." Indeed, after the age of 30, many people grow up independently. Western culture promotes adolescence as a period they don't want to live in, need social approval from their peers, sense of direction in life, and separation from parents. Deeper but for many, adolescence is a period of lifelong friendships, high friendships, idealism, and a sense of life's great possibilities before adulthood. Adolescence begins with puberty, that is, our sexual maturity. Puberty follows a surge in hormones that can boost mood and kicks off two years of rapid physical development. It usually starts at the age of 11 for girls and 13 for boys.

Periods and stages of adulthood

When people turn forty, they are entering adulthood, a time when they realize that life is not ahead, but behind. Some psychologists say that for many people, midlife is a time of crisis, great struggle, regret, or even life. But the truth told by

people is that by the age of forty, the incidence of unhappiness, job loss, family discord, divorce, anxiety and suicide does not increase. Life events begin to transition to new stages of life at different ages. Social Hours - The definition of the "right time" to leave home, get a job, get married, have children, and retire varies from era to century and culture to culture. In Western Europe, less than 10 percent of men over 65 are working, compared to 16 percent in the United States, 36 percent in Japan, and 69 percent in Mexico.

Conclusion: To live is to grow up. This means that every moment you are the oldest and from now on you are the youngest. This means that we can all look back with satisfaction or regret, and look forward with hope and fear. From adolescence to middle age, people typically develop a sense of identity, self-confidence, and self-esteem. We must remember that life requires stability and change. Stability allows us to depend on others, secures our identity, and fosters our interest in the healthy development of children. Change awakens our concerns about current influences, supports our hope for a brighter future, and allows us to adapt and grow with experience.

References:

1. Mayers "Psychology" book
2. Ghaziyev. E.G. "General Psychology". Tashkent. 2007. 1-2 books
3. Maklakov. A.G. "Obshaya psychology" M.; "Peter" 2003
4. <http://www.wikipedia.org>
5. <http://www.ziyonet.uz>
6. www.natlib.uz
7. www.fikr.uz

